

Making Sense of Memories

REDMIX
Online Seminar Series

18 March 2026 • 17:00 CET

Doing Ethnography among Ghosts: Memory, Silence and Invisibility

Paolo Favero (University of Antwerp)

25 March 2026 • 17:00 CET

Oral History and Audio: Voices and Sounds for Storytelling

Francesca Berardi (Chora Media & Will Media)

31 March 2026 • 17:00 CEST

Along the Borders of the Film Archive: Views of the Ottoman Empire

Elif Rongen-Kaynakçı (Eye Filmmuseum - Amsterdam)

Organized & moderated by **Francesco Dragone** (University of Turin)

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